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**PERFORMING EMOTIONS:
*BHAKTI, LOVE AND DESIRE IN JAGOI RAAS***

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In the radio play, *Kaorabara raas sanabagi ahingdo* (Do you remember that night of *raas*), MK Binodini uses *raas* as a metaphor for an illicit relationship between the two protagonists. The story revolves around an unexpected meeting between a middle-aged unmarried man and his love interest of one time, who also happens to be a relative. As conversation reluctantly began between the two, they confront about what both feels as unrequited love. They talk of a night when the whole family, including the lady had gone to watch *jagoi raas*. He had stayed back to keep watch of the house. That night turned intimate after she returned home suddenly feigning illness. Using the literal meaning of *raas*, as in the night of *jagoi raas* performance, the writer implicitly hints at the intimate relationship between the two characters by

using *raas* as a metaphor. Since *jagoi raas* depicts the love play between Krishna, Radha and gopis, and their secret rendezvous in the middle of the night, *raas* is often used to refer to adulterous, intimate, and forbidden interactions. While explaining the stories of *jagoi raas* at Government Dance College¹, an *oja* (teacher) once remarked, “these are shameful stories if we really think about it”.

What makes these stories shameful is a cultural sensibility that tend to sanitize the notions of love from its romantic and physical desires. For a devout Vaishnava, and performers of *jagoi raas*, it is a religious and ritual offering where implications of love and desire transcend the material world. Any usage and interpretation of *jagoi raas* as something belonging to ordinary

humanely realm is countered by other interpretations of *jagoi raas* as a “divine love play”. The classification of love as divine sheds love from its ordinary meanings of romantic and erotic love. The tussle between the “divine” and ordinary love is also evident in the sharp distinction made between *bhakti* (devotional love) and *shringa r* (erotic love) in the theory of performing arts. *Jagoi raas* emphasizes on performing, or rather embodying the essence of *bhakti* by restraining the body movements, use of garments like *maikhum* (veil), *thabakyat* (a white cloth to cover the chest), and minimal use of facial expressions. Even though the content is based on the love play, the performance of it is meditative and geared towards attaining spiritual union that transcend the physical bodies of the performers and the devotees.

The aesthetic sensibility reflected in the costumes of *jagoi raas*, the choreographic choices and the overall dramaturgy contribute to the fashioning of *jagoi raas* as a sacred performance. In the process of making it sacred, love is defined in terms of devotional love (*bhakti*), the longing as a spiritual quest of the devotees and the bliss brought by the union of finite soul with the infinite. The first segment of the paper delves into this process to understand how *bhakti* conceptualizes love as divine and

¹Government Dance College, Palace Compound, Imphal, is one major site where the researcher conducted her ethnographic research.

devotional. In *bhakti*, there is an inherent quest of the devotee to unite with the God where one is required to surrender one's ego and any sense of "I". The second segment of the paper focusses on this aspect of constant longing for union that is further accentuated by an inherent possibility of separation. For this, the paper draws from an experience of performing in a *jagoi raas (maharaas)* at the Govindaji temple, Imphal.

***Bhakti*/devotion and conceptualization of love as divine**

In modern scholarship, *bhakti* has been defined as a social movement against the structures of caste and Brahminical supremacy (Veer, 1987; Das, 2003), as well as an act of personal devotion and an individual longing for God (Novetzke, 2007). Veer (1987) believes that the former definition arises from an essentialist interpretation of the real and sociological meaning of *bhakti* that tends to blur the differences between asceticism and devotionism. Devotionism, in fact, emphasizes on caste distinctions whereas asceticism tends to minimize it. However, what interests us here is the second understanding of *bhakti* that is defined by a personal act of devotion. The personal act does not entirely mean a strictly private affair but is something accompanied by a public of reception or an audience (Novetzke, 2007). Everything takes place in the presence of an audience, at least the God himself, if not anyone else.

Bhakti, derived from the root word *bhaj*, is roughly translated as love and devotion. *Bhakti* or devotion was popularized through telling and re-telling of literary forms and through performative expressions in the form of songs, theatre, dances and so on. Especially in Gaudiya Vaishnava tradition of which *jagoi raas* is a part of, devotion is frenzied worship through songs and dances, performance of an ecstasy and sometimes an "excess" like a mad lover (Das, 2003). The spread of *bhakti* in medieval India, whether it be through literary or non-literary traditions such as performances, involved core narratives despite the regional differences (Novetzke,

2007). One of the core narratives of *bhakti* is an ultimate, selfless devotion to God, a longing to be one with the God, surrender of one's ego and pride, and a feeling of "pure" love towards the God. A selfless love, devoid of lust and any physicality of humanely world has been conceptualized as "divine" and *bhakti* sustains on this understanding of love as divine. Radha's love, or love between Gopis and Krishna is divine and hence their play or the *raas leela* is a divine play that is devoid of any romantic or erotic connotations.

The origin of *bhakti* in the form of a feeling of wonderment and awe at divine power and devotion it inspired, can be traced to Rigveda (Nadkarni, 2007). Bhagvad Gita recognized *bhakti* as another important path to attain God in addition to the path of work (*karma*) and knowledge (*gyana*). The mythology of cowherd Krishna in Srimad Bhagvad, a character different from the tactical Krishna as we see in Gita, contributed further to conceptualization of *bhakti* as devotion in the form of love. Given the influence of Sufism, the Alvars of South India and many others on the pan-Indian *bhakti* movement, scholars have pointed out that the projection of God as a beloved is prevalent in writings across religion and sects. For instance, Rabia of Basara, a female Sufi saint is considered as someone who enunciated the doctrine of divine love (Das, 2003). Similarly, the imagery of divine lover and the devotee as a mad lover can be found in the poetry of great Tamil Saiva poet, Manikka Vachakar, mystic poet Rumi, Guru Nanak and so on. It must also be noted that God does not always assume the form of a beloved but can also appear as a friend (*sakhya*) or child (loved through *vatsyala* or motherly love) or master towards whom a devotee surrenders as a servant (*dasya*).

In Gaudiya Vaishnavism, there are two axiological elements- passion and humility, that constitute the ethical core of *bhakti* or devotion (Schweig, 2002). An awe for the greatness of the deity creates an atmosphere of deep reverence and humble admiration among the followers. The absence and presence of God intensifies the humility and passion of devotion, each one further complementing and augmenting

the other. It is in anticipation of the immanent absence that the humility in service and passionate devotion are heightened. It is considered that devotional love in separation (*viraha bhakti*) or performing service while having attained distance (*vipralambha*) are the highest form of intimacy with the deity. Separation or distance is most intensively positive experience of union, paradoxically, and not the negative experience associated with the way lovers of this world agonize when apart. Passionate loving service to Krishna like the way gopis serve Krishna in the *raas leela* is understood as the highest form of devotion. The highest relationship with God, or *rasa*, is that of *shringara*, the relationship consisting of the passionate love that is found in a lover for his or her beloved. However, any sense of passionate love involving humanely desires is conceived as unethical, immoral, or corrupting the essence of love in *bhakti*. Among the specialists in the Chaitanya tradition, it has been argued how God, the source of righteousness, can also be the amorous deity of Krishna whose affairs with the Gopis appear to be “unethical” (Schweig, 2002).

The sense of “unethical” love and degradation of practices involving the physicality or body can be exemplified by the case of *Sahajiya* Vaishnavas. Sarbadhikary (2015) finds that throughout her fieldwork among the Vaishnava community in Bengal, *Sahajiyas* have been stigmatized for their practices that involves physical relationships among married partners and illicit relationships with gurus. Despite *Sahajiyas* claim of belonging to Vaishnava community, their practices are considered disgusting. *Sahajiyas* also follow the teachings of Chaitanya, but not in terms of sanitized space of spiritual imagination but through the direct use of their physical bodies (Sarbadhikary, 2015). For a *sahajiya*, emphasis is on experiencing the *sahaj* that implies an affective disposition of savoring the primeval state of man (Krishna) and woman (Radha) union through heightened bodily sensations. Their practice is not characterized by outer realm but relies on cultivation of an interiorized bodily space and to experience Radha-Krishna’s pleasures within their own physical bodies. *Sahajiyas* conceptualize their body as a sacred place, a “veiled Vrindavan” where pleasures and ecstasy are felt and experienced.

Another interpretation of love and desire can be found in the psychoanalytic reading of Krishna-Radha's story. Kakar (1986) describes how "divine" love is different from the common notions of love characterised by eroticism. The difference, however, does not lie in the absence of physical union but in the presence of sustained feeling of excitement and pleasure. Kakar writes that the absence of lust in Radha's love for Krishna does not mean an absence of desire, but simply of the ultimate sense of pleasure. Quoting the work of anthropologist Frederic Marglin, Kakar adds that one of Krishna's names is *acyuta* meaning "the one whose seed does not fall". The meaning associated with the retention of seed is love that "exist for itself, in itself" which is very different from the momentary everyday experience of love and physical desire. Though Kakar's conceptualisation of divine love does not side-line the centrality of the body, it emphasises on the definition of love beyond its ordinary understanding. On the whole, any interpretation of Krishna-Radha's love involving physical desires is conceived as derailing the essence of love in *bhakti*. There is an emphasis on love that is divine, meaning something that does not include any form of humanely desires and physical longing. Love as defined in *bhakti* also marks itself differently from tantric philosophy that focuses on primitive communalism in terms of eating together, ritual equality of women and freedom of physical communion (Gohain, 1987).

Similarly, among the Vaishnavas of Manipur, *bhakti* is devoid of anything "unethical" and is defined in terms of "pure" and "divine". They consider that *bhakti* is the distinguishing feature of Manipuri Vaishnava culture. It is *bhakti* or rather the performance of *bhakti* that renders *jagoi raas* and Manipuri culture different from *raas leelas* of other regions of the country. There is a serene and subtle demeanor that places humility to a higher pedestal. Manipuri dance as an embodiment of the *bhakti* sensibility is described by a noted scholar, Elangbam Nilakanta, as "subdued eloquence". While teaching *jagoi raas*, the teachers would emphasize on things like "*wakhal choithoktaba*" (avoidance of distractions), "*wakhal seranba khandaba*" (avoidance of unwanted thoughts), "*pukning fathaba*" (control of senses), "*erang*

yaodaba” (devoid of lust and desire). The devotees and dancers are expected to maintain a humble attitude and present themselves in ultimate reverence to the Supreme God. Love between Radha, Krishna and Gopis is also defined as “platonic love”. It is, therefore, considered a complete misinterpretation if it involves any humanely understanding of love. “There is always a danger of misinterpretation/shallow interpretation when stories of Radha-Krishna are told to someone incapable of grasping its philosophical and spiritual depth” (Thangjam Dasrath, personal communication, July 28, 2023).

Among the Manipuri Vaishnavas, offering of *jagoi raas* is done to prepare their own space of Brindavan in their courtyard. In their pavilion, they offer *jagoi raas*, and the holy space where the performance took place is marked sacred. When person dies, the dead body is temporary placed at this sacred area symbolising the union with the Lord in Brindaban (Laishram Sarat, personal communication, August 17, 2023). Aribam Chitreswar Sharma, a scholar, and a former member of the Govindaji Temple Board voiced his displeasure with the way that the stories of Krishna-Radha and *jagoi raas* were interpreted in the ordinary meanings of love and desire. Like many others, he believes that there is no lust or physical desire in Radha and Krishna's relationship. Rather, their relationship is based on pure love. He views the sensual portrayal of this relationship as incomprehensible. For the Vaishanava community, *jagoi raas* is a divine play rather than merely a drama involving regular people (Devi, 2010). This is one of the reasons for selecting children to perform as Krishna and Radha. Girls in their prepubescent years are viewed as pure since their bodies is considered “impure” once they start menstruating. This emphasis on a body free of corporeal cravings and emasculated pleasure is how *bhakti* elevates love to the divine.

In *jagoi raas*, this essence of *bhakti* or devotion is understood as the complete surrender of one’s identity, ego, feeling of I (*ei haiba wakhhal se thadokpa*) and giving up of all ideas of possession and ownership. Love is without tarnished mind. This goes same for love in Sufi tradition where differences are marked between *ishq*

(romantic) and *mohabbat* (divine). In interpreting love as divine, there has been reformulation of *shringara* (erotic love) into *bhakti* (devotion) (Behl, 2007). Though devotional frenzy saints and devotees used the framework of love poetry just as we see in the songs of *jagoi raas*, deeper spiritual understanding can be achieved through an understanding of a higher philosophy of love in *bhakti*. It is also that this framework of love poetry has its inherent dangers of obliterating the distinction between the passion of human love and the raptures of divine love (Das, 2003). According to this framework, outer structure could be love poem whereas its inner structure is religious and spiritual. Therefore, the reformulation of *shringara* into *bhakti* is one major way of making the love divine and thereby shedding from it every sense of humanely passion. This reformulation is manifested in the way dances are choreographed, decorum is set, and the performances organized. *Jagoi raas* is no exception to this reformulation since similar trends are present in the history of Bharatanatyam dances of Devadasi tradition was sanitized to craft the modern repertoire of Bharatanatyam. The following section picks up the features of longing, separation and union as defined in *bhakti* to see how these emotions are crafted in the *jagoi raas* performance.

***Bhakti, love, and desire in maharaas*²**

“When I first took part in maharaas, I dozed off during Krishna antardhyaan (Krishna’s disappearance). I did not know fully understand the significance of the segment. I gradually began to understand after I started learning jagoi raas and maharaas in my dance classes. Until then I did not realise how beautiful and soulful this segment is.”

- (excerpt from an interview with a dancer/participant)

²*Maharaas* is one of the five types of *jagoi raas* that is offered/performed on the full moon of *Hiyangei*. The other four *jagoi raas* are *kunja raas*, *basanta raas*, *nitya raas* and *diba raas*.

“I could not locate you (the researcher) during the performance. With seventy-eighty gopis in similar costumes, with their faces covered in transparent veil, the dancers somehow seem faceless, one merging into the other. Everyone appears one and the same. It becomes hard to distinguish. If I think I spotted you, then you disappear the very next moment.”

- (excerpt from an interview with an audience)

“I sing the songs of maharaas in my daily prayers, I haven’t forgotten any. I want to offer an *eko gopi eko shyam*³ in my courtyard, only then I can die in peace.”

- (excerpt from an interview with ninety-six year old, *Ima* Madhabi, a *jagoi raas* exponent)

What could possibly connect these excerpts? Each instance tells of different ways of relating to *maharaas* in ways intelligible to them. A peculiar feature of *maharajas* is Krishna *antardhyan* meaning Krishna’s disappearance from the performance space. During this segment, the lights in the performance area is dimmed, the participants gather and sit in the periphery while Radha and *gopi akhanabi* (select *gopis*) sing songs in search of Krishna. It lasts for about half an hour. The young dancer in the first excerpt most probably participated to gain practical understanding of *maharaas*. She could be mentally occupied with the act of dancing instead of spiritual and philosophical nuances. Or maybe she is tired after an extensive preparation of dressing up in *kumin potloi*. Or kneeling inside the *kumin* for more than half an hour might have been painful. I can tell from my experience that it is indeed so. Most of the dance participants, at least the ones I talked to, have faint or little idea about what

³*Eko gopi eko Shyam* meaning “one Krishna for each gopi” is the final segment of *maharaas* where each gopi/devotee is considered to have attained union with Krishna as they dance together. The phrase is commonly used as another name for *maharaas*.

was going on. Many did not know the relationship between dimming of the lights and Krishna's disappearance. Since the whole sequence of the performance are not taught during the rehearsals, many participants experience the performance for the first time, learning as they dance along.

The very essence of *jagoi raas* or *maharaas* and the idea of *bhakti* is contingent upon understanding the significance of "disappearance" and "(re)appearance". It is in the constant longing to be united with Him that devotion or love is sustained. The audience mentioned in the second excerpt is someone known to me. I had invited him so that a follow up interview could be scheduled to get an idea of audience's perspective. The "faceless" as signified by inability to locate one particular person, the resemblance of one to the other, and constant shift between appearance and disappearance guide the principle of devotion or *bhakti*. Everyone is equal and same in the eyes of the God. The innumerable *gopis* do not have a face but appear one and the same to Him. Love for God and an intense longing to be one with Him involves the love in separation and love in union. The separation and union, the possibility of separation or pain of separation is what makes the longing intense resulting to a heightened passion of the devotees. In union, or in appearance, there is inherent possibility of losing Him or his disappearance that humbles the devotees. The disappearance and (re)appearance is similar to pangs and pleasure of separation (*viraha*) and union (*milan/sambhog*). It reminds the devotees of the possibility of losing the God if they are unable to control their self-pride and ego.

Maharaas is one of the five kinds of *jagoi raas* performed on the full moon of *Hiyangei*. *Maharaas* is based on the five chapters (29-33) of the tenth book of Srimad Bhagavad known as *Ras Panchadhyaya*. The five chapters are considered to be the heart of the Shrimad Bhagavad. The five chapters describe – gopi's coming to meet Krishna and Krishna's disappearance at the end, the gopi's search for Krishna, gopis singing the songs of separation, Krishna's re-appearance and union, and the *raas* dance respectively. *Maharaas* begins with Krishna's flute as an intimation of their

rendezvous. Gopis, on hearing the sweet sound of Krishna's flute, left whatever they were doing and proceed towards the bower to play *raas* with Krishna. *Ras Panchadhyaya* explains that those who could not leave due to societal constraints of marriage meditated and sent their souls instead. And, for some, Krishna arranged temporarily exhibits in the form of material bodies to leave beside their husbands.

In *maharaas* performance, the verses of *Ras Panchadhyaya* are either sung or spoken. Following the story as given in the said text, *maharaas* begins with a captivating melody of a locally produced flute played on slender bamboo, known as *toudri*. *Gopis* (dancers) enter the *raas mandali* as songs of *gopi abhisar* (gopi's coming towards their meeting place) are sung by *sutradhari* (singers). The songs and verses are still rendered in Sanskrit and Bengali at Govindaji temple whereas Manipuri rendering of songs are used also in *jagoi raas* at other performance spaces. On gopis' arrival, the man playing Krishna (who sits outside the main performance area) chants a verse from the first chapter of *Ras Panchadhyaya* where Krishna asks the gopis to return to their respective homes. Upon hearing this, the gopis turn their back, stand with their heads down and rub their toes on the ground. The teachers explained that this act signify gopis' embarrassment and displeasure at Krishna's instruction to return home. Apart from asking them to return to their respective homes, the verses are meant to remind the gopis of their duties towards their husbands. They are informed that no good woman would have small-time adulterous liaisons that could damage her reputation. Krishna then advises them that mere physical proximity to him is not the only way to attain Him but can be done through devotional process of hearing his glories, worshipping his deity form and by meditating on Him.

The *sutradharis* (singers) recite lyrically the verses explaining plight of gopis who are silently bearing the burden of unhappiness. The verses describe gopis' unflinching attachment to Him despite Him speaking unfavourably. The gopis wipe their tears, turn back again and began to speak. The verses of gopis in response to

Krishna's instruction are recited by eight dancers (selected during rehearsals) symbolising eight close friends of Radha. These verses are plea to Krishna not to say such cruel words, and to reciprocate their devotion with His love and blessings. Krishna, after hearing *gopis'* pleas, began to play and dance with them. *Gopis'* start to think of themselves as special ones blessed by Him. When this thought took shape as pride in *gopis'* mind, Krishna humbled them by suddenly disappearing from the performance area. In the first disappearance, Krishna takes one special *gopi* along with him. The names and character of this chosen *gopi* is not specified in *Ras Panchadhyaya* but later writings identify this particular *gopi* with Radha. Radha, on being chosen as the special one is filled with pride. This leads to Krishna's disappearance leaving Radha behind. The episode of Krishna's disappearance is called Krishna *antardhyan*. No dancers take the role of Krishna in *maharajas* at Govindaji temple. To symbolise Krishna's disappearance, the lights in the performance space is dimmed until the segment of Krishna's (re)appearance.

As described in chapter thirty and thirty-one, the *akhanabi gopis* (select *gopis*) along with the girl dancing as Radha sings songs of separation in search of Krishna. In *maharaas*, the performance reaches this segment little before midnight. By the time Krishna *antardhyan* happens the ambience of the temple is couched in chilly silence. Along with the dimming of light, the percussion, flute and esraj stop playing. It is only the voice of *gopis* that fills the place. From my experience of participating in *maharaas*, I remember the silence brought about by dimming of lights was broken by soulful voice of the *sutradhari(s)*. *Sutradhari oja* ArambamTombinou, *oja* Sagolsem Jasoda and *oja* Laipubam Bino, the seasoned singers with experience of a lifetime, successively recited the verses in a way that sound sweet yet weighed down by deep sadness. The girl taking the role of Radha sat facing the idols and sang as a plea to Krishna to come back. Her voice, with childlike sweetness and innocence filled the performance space. Against the darkness and silence of the night, her voice, devoid of any instrumental add-ons, felt as if one is hearing someone singing/humming from a distance. The manner in which *sutradhari* recited, or the

gopis and Radha sang all culminate to what they call “*prem pokhanba*”, meaning arousing a feeling of deep and intense affection.

Most senior devotees feel that this is the most emotional segment of *maharajas* and hence making it one of the most special *raas* among its five kinds. An old *malini*⁴ recounted her youthful days when she took part in *jagoi raas*. She said, “the sweetest of all is *maharaas*, it is hard not to cry during Krishna *antardhyan*, one gets overwhelmed by emotions of “*gopi geet*”. For a Vaishnava, it is believed that it is in this feeling of sadness, and the act of crying where they experience the highest spiritual bliss. It is no easy thing. It is not mere crying but involves an imagination of Krishna as a lover to whom one completely surrenders. An example of *gopis*’ admiration of Krishna can be seen in the following verse:

*O hero, kindly distribute to us the nectar of your lips,
Which enhances conjugal pleasures and vanquishes grief.
The nectar is thoroughly relished by your vibrating flute
And makes people forget any other attachment.*
(Srimad Bhagavatam, trans. 1995, p. 568)

The chapter of separation is followed by the chapter of (re)union. In (re)union, Krishna appears again and performs the *raas* dance with the gopis. After their separation from him, the *gopis* were greatly concerned when Krishna appeared to them once more. The *gopis* conveyed to him their intense sentiments of ecstasy after he comforted them. The union of Radha and gopis with Krishna is called *sambhog*, and is followed by *swadhin*. While *sambhog* denotes union *swadhin* denotes a feeling of liberation. *Sambhog*, however, is presented in a non-sexual form as the union of souls which results in *swadhin* i.e. the liberation of soul from the worldly pleasures. Just as love does not connote the ordinary love, the union is the union of souls that transcends the physical body. The dols or image of Radha-Krishna besides on another

⁴women who makes garlands and flower arrangements at the Govindaji temple.

is worshipped as a divine form of love and is described as “*yugal oire*” meaning the two have united as one.

In the final chapter of *Ras Panchadhyaya*, Krishna performs *raas* with the *gopis*. Each *gopi* feels that Krishna is dancing next to him. Krishna multiplies himself and makes sure each *gopi* gets her own Krishna. *Maha Raas* culminates in *eko gopi eko shyam* (one Krishna for each *gopi*). It signifies attainment of Krishna to whom the *gopis* surrendered with utmost devotion. *Jagoi raas* generally culminates in the union of Krishna and *gopis*, especially of Radha with Krishna. After episodes of separation and sadness, a Vaishnava in Manipur considers witnessing the final union of Krishna Radha in *jagoi raas* as their own personal attainment of God. To a devotee, *jagoi raas* is a living embodiment of their Lord’s divine plays. For oja Kshetrimayum Thouranishabi, who is a *sutradhari/raas* associated with Govindaji temple, *maharajas* holds an immense importance to her devotional practice and religiosity (Kshetrimayum Thouranishabi, personal communication, July 31, 2023). Her first association with Govindaji *jagoi raas* was through her enactment as Radha in *maharaas*. She started dancing as Radha at the age of nine. Though Alzheimer has hit her now, she remembers the verse she was once taught by her teacher. When I asked about her memories of dancing in *jagoi raas*, oja Thouranishabi said that she has endless things to tell. Due to her sickness and old age, she keeps repeating a segment from her memory, starting another round of re-telling after maintaining silence for couple of minutes. Interestingly, each re-telling begins with the verse of Radha in *maharaas* she used to recite. She would then ask whether *maharaas* season already. Oja Thouranishabi, even with her hunched back, said, “I can still dance in *maharaas* if given a light *kumin potloi*. I just want to dance among the *gopis* and serve Him one last time.” Oja Thouranishabi’s devotion is mixed with the fervour of a lover who is eager to meet her beloved. Similarly for *Ima Madhabi* in the third excerpt, being able to witness *eko gopi eko shyam* of *maharajas* will be similar to attaining her Lord. It is a way of attaining him through a sensorial experience of watching/offering/performing a *jagoi raas*.

There are four crucial points to be noted in connection to love and devotion. First, *gopis* leave their homes upon hearing Krishna's flute. They abandon their duties, their husbands and family. This is interpreted in *bhakti* as renunciation of material possession and worldly pleasures in pursuit of the Supreme. Secondly, mention is also made of those who could not leave their homes due to norms and moral constraints. Among the *raas* practitioners, these *gopis* are called *gopi chithabi*, meaning those who have been left out. As a way of compensating their fate, it is believed that they are the ones who reach/ meet Krishna first. This signifies the transcendence of physical bodies and the emphasis of a spiritual union. Thirdly, Krishna's disappearance serves as a lesson for devotees to surrender their ego and embody humility. It also serves as a way of heightening one's passion by making them experience love in separation. Fourth, Krishna constantly reminds the *gopis* about their duties as a woman/wife. He advises them of righteousness and moral responsibilities, about what makes a woman good or bad. All the four interpretations and meanings associated to each act are also to defend the righteousness of Krishna and prevent attachment of any "unethical" meanings to *raas*. According to some narratives, *gopis* are considered as creation of Krishna from his own body. Therefore, any act of intimacy, passion and desire cannot be deemed immoral or unethical since it does not involve any other woman. In another interpretation, the nameless special *gopi* with whom Krishna disappears is characterised as Radha to make the union legitimate. Both meanings contribute in subverting the notion of unethical or to convert the seemingly immoral to an ethical act.

In *bhakti*, devotional love directed towards the God involves a constant longing to unite with Him. The amorous dalliances of Krishna and his love play with *gopis* are made sacred by defining them as divine. The divine play gets enacted in *jagoi raas* where *gopis* longing for Krishna is considered as manifestation of a devotee's longing. The union of *gopis* and Krishna is described as spiritual union transcending the physical realm of the human. The love, devotion, *gopis*' desire to be one with Krishna, their union, all of these culminate to something that transcends the physical

body. Any interpretation of earthly and humanely love, then, is considered to dilute the spiritual and philosophical fervour of divine love. This further complicates the notions of what is ethical or unethical love, and why is ordinary definitions of love and desire overlooked in an attempt to understand the philosophical depth of *jagoi raas*. The answer partly lies in the tendency to sanitise the definitions of love and a desire to create something sacred out of it.

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